

Composition and Stability of Iron (III) -7- Bromo -8- Hydroxy-quinoline -5- Sulphonic Acid Chelate

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Albert and Magrath¹ found that many metal ions did not form a precipitate but changed colour with 8-hydroxyquinoline-5-sulphonic acid. 7-bromo-8-hydroxyquinoline-5-sulphonic acid also shows colour changes with a number of metal ions. In these investigations, 7-bromo-8-hydroxyquinoline-5-sulphonic acid was prepared by the method used by Banerji and Srivastava² and Tiao Hsu Chang³. The complex formation between this reagent and ferric chloride is instantaneous. The composition of the complex was studied spectrophotometrically and the stability constants and free energy of formation have also been calculated.

EXPERIMENTAL AND RESULTS

A standard solution of iron was prepared from a sample of ferric chloride (B.D.H.). A purified sample of 7-bromo-8-hydroxyquinoline-5-sulphonic acid was used. Absorbance measurements were made on Hilger- Uvispec spectrophotometer (Model H 700-380) fitted with a thermostated jacket using one cm. effective light path and pH was measured on a Beckman pH meter (Model H2). All the measurements were made at 20° and $\mu = 0.1 M$ and the chelate formed was studied under optimum conditions.

Solutions containing the same concentrations ($2 \times 10^{-4} M$) of the reagent and ferric chloride were prepared at different pH and at $\mu = 0.1 M$ maintained with NaClO_4 and the absorbance at various wavelengths were taken. The complex showed λ_{max} at 430 nm in the pH range 2-4. pH 3 was selected for subsequent studies.

The nature of the complex formed was determined by the method of Vosburgh and Cooper⁴ at pH 3.0 ± 0.1 and $\mu = 0.1 M$. Only one complex is formed under the conditions of study, with a λ_{max} in the region of 430 nm (fig. 1).

As has been said before, the composition of the complex as determined by three different methods; Job's method of Continuous Variation⁵, mole-ratio method⁶ and Slope-ratio method⁷, at pH 3.0 ± 0.1 and $\mu = 0.1 M$ was found to be 1 : 2.

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Evaluation of the Stability Constants : For the purpose of the determination of the stability constants of the complex, calculations have been made by the method used by Banerji and Dey⁸ and the mole-ratio method⁶. The values of $\log K$ obtained were $\log K = 9.28 \pm 0.19$ at $pH\ 3.0 \pm 0.1$, $\mu = 0.1\ M$ and at 20° and ΔF° , the free energy of formation comes out to be $-12.45 \pm 0.25\ Kcals/mole$ at 20° .

FIG. 1

Fig. 1. Absorption-spectra of the mixture of ferric-chloride and 7-bromo-8-hydroxyquinoline-5-sulphonic acid at $pH\ 3.0 \pm 0.1$ and at $\mu = 0.1\ M$.

Curve 1 : Reagent alone $C = 0$; $C' = 3.2 \times 10^{-4}\ M$.

2 : $C = 3.2 \times 10^{-4}\ M$; $p = 1$.

3 : $C = 1.6 \times 10^{-4}\ M$; $p = 2$.

4 : $C = 1.06 \times 10^{-4}\ M$; $p = 3$.

5 : $C = 8.0 \times 10^{-5}\ M$; $p = 4$.

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